

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

INCREASING THE RESOURCE OF ARROW SWITCHES BY IMPROVING THE ATTACHMENT OF THE ARROW RAIL ELEMENTS TO THE BASE

1.Umaraliyev Shohjahon Maxamadro'zi o'g'li

2.Embergenov Avezmurat Bekmuratovich

Assistants of the Tashkent State transport University.

Abstract: This article provides information on how to remove a new type of fasteners of stretch conductors. In this regard, it was reflected that the problems of improving elements of a higher structure, such as connections and intersections of Railways, took a special place.

Keywords: screw, lining, welded pad, elastic terminal, wit, frame rail, terminal bolt, nut, elastic washer, terminal, rib.

INTRODUCTION. The relevance of the article is determined by the needs of our country's economic growth, requiring accelerated development of transport. In order to ensure increasing railway transportation, to create conditions for the most efficient use of all the advantages of railway transport, to increase the speed and weight of trains, it is necessary to advance the pace of development of the track, its strengthening and improvement [1]. In this regard, a special place is occupied by the problems of improving such elements of the upper structure as

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

connections and intersections of rail tracks [2]. This is explained by their design features, which determine the specifics of interaction with rolling stock and the features of train traffic on them. In the development of railway switch designs in Uzbekistan, it should be noted that there is a tendency to introduce more powerful translation elements – wits and crosses, which, in turn, require their reliable attachment to the base [3,4,5,6,7,8,9]. Currently, about 10 thousand switches are operated on the roads of the main railway transport. Several dozen types of arrow products are used. Their designs and technology of use must meet the needs of the transportation process.

The purpose of the article is, based on modern approaches, to develop a method for obtaining effective and economical technical solutions for the construction of pads with a cushion for the arrows of mass-scale switch designs, which allows to obtain an effect at minimal cost for their implementation. At the same time, the solutions obtained should preserve the general technological schemes for the manufacture of elements used at Russian switch plants. The whole effect should be achieved by increasing the engineering level of technical solutions. These solutions should contribute to improving the quality of switches, reducing the cost of materials for their manufacture and operating costs. Achieving the goal involves developing specific research objectives. The objectives of the study are: analysis of the operational qualities of the elements of attachment of wits and frame rails to the base on the basis of direct dynamic strength tests, analysis of

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

the causes of failures of pads with a pillow in operation, metallographic studies of the lining with a pillow in the fracture sections in order to determine the causes of the appearance and development of defects, development of methods for calculating the stress-strain state of the lining with a pillow and obtaining on the basis of these studies the optimal technical solution, the formation of proposals for the use of the developed option. The scientific novelty of the work consists in the fact that in the course of the study, experimental and theoretical developments were carried out for the first time to study the effect of the design of fasteners on the arrow of the switch on their resource. Comparative results of dynamic strength tests of pads with a cushion of various designs for determining their stress-strain state under the influence of trains, taking into account the peculiarities of different manufacturing technologies, are obtained. The analysis of the service life of the elements of attachment of wits and frame rails to the base is presented. A probabilistic model of the operation of metal linings with a pillow of arrow switches is constructed, which is in good agreement with the results of experimental operation, which allows us to calculate the distribution of failures of linings with a pillow depending on the characteristics of the metal from which they are made, the initial tightening of the fasteners and the spectrum of stresses arising from the train load. Dependences of failures of pads with a pillow are obtained using the developed technique, which makes it possible to plan the replacement of pads on switches when changing the main metal parts. The study revealed new

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

types of defects of the causes of failures of pads with a pillow. To identify the causes of the fracture of the pads with a pillow, chemical analysis and metallographic studies of the lining with a pillow in the sections of the fractures were performed.

METHOD. In modern conditions, one of the most relevant areas is research to increase the resource and stability of the switches and their elements [10,11,12,13,14,15]. Important elements that determine the resource and stable operation of 13 switches are fasteners. In the arrow zone, such elements are pads with pillows, on which the wits of the arrow translation rely. Pads with a pillow are made using various technologies (Figure 1.1). The purpose of pads with a pillow is to transfer the load from the rolling stock to the beam and create conditions for moving the sole of the wits when transferring them from one position to another [16,17,18].

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

Figure 1.1 - The scheme of fixing the lining with a pillow on the arrow of the switch

1 — screw; 2 — lining; 3 — welded pad; 4 — elastic terminal; 5 — wit; 6 — frame rail; 7 — terminal bolt; 8— nut; 9 — elastic washer; 10 — terminal; 11 — rib.

Linings with a pillow attached to the rivet lining have been for a long time the only design used on switches of all types and brands (Figures 1.2-1.3). Having proven performance qualities, linings with a pillow on rivets have disadvantages associated with the breakdown of rivet connections, which leads to failures in the operation of linings with rivets cushion and rivet connections.

Figure 1.2 - The design of the arrow of the switch, equipped with pads with a cushion on rivets.

Figure 1.3 - Cushion lining made using rivet technology.

During operation, failures of the pads with a cushion on the rivets occur due to the weakening of the rivet joints, cracks and fractures of the pads passing through the rivet holes in the area of the inner edge of the sole of the frame rails, crumpling and wear of the pillows. The appearance and development of defects in the pads with a pillow on the rivets, leads not only to failures in the work of the pads themselves with a pillow, but also prevent the transfer of the wits of the arrows. The technology used in their manufacture does not fully ensure the operational stability of the fasteners that meets modern operational requirements [11].

Figure 2 shows a typical fracture of the pads with a cushion on the rivets.

Figure 2 - The fracture of the lining with a cushion on the rivets.

RESULT. For such solutions, we have made the following improvements. The easiest way to modify the design is to remove holes from the lining for welding the pillow. The welding of the pillow in this version is carried out by two longitudinal seams along the long sides of the pillow (Figure 2.1).

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

Figure 2.1 - Lining with a welded pad without holes in the lining.

Another promising way to modify the structure is to switch to a solid construction in which the lining and the pillow are one part (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2 - Molded lining with a narrowed cushion.

CONCLUSION. The task of increasing the resource of the arrow switches by improving the attachment of the rail elements of the arrow to the base, namely the lining with a pillow, has been set and solved. The main factor determining the performance of pads with a pillow is their design.

Improvement of strength and performance characteristics of pads with a pillow can be achieved by:

- applications of metal with higher strength characteristics;
- changes in the design of pads with a pillow by increasing the thickness of the lining plate and (or) the introduction of special design solutions (for example, unloading chips) that reduce the concentration of stresses;
- changes in the technology of manufacturing pads with a pillow, by

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/>
реестр:1070589

eliminating technological holes and removing thermal nodes from the locations of stress concentrators;

- the use of fundamentally new pads with a pillow due to new technical solutions, in particular due to the use of cast construction.

REFERENCE

1. Умаралиев Ш.М., Джаббаров С.Т. ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТЕМИР ЙЎЛЛАРИ” АЖ ТЕЗЮРАР ВА ЮҚОРИ ТЕЗЛИКДАГИ ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ УЧАСТКАЛАРИДА ЯНГИ ТУРДАГИ БИРИКТИРГИЧЛАРНИНГ ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШИ. Материалы конференции International Scientific-Practical Distance Conference «The 21st Century Skills for Professional Activity». 2021/5/15 (Vol. 5, 212-214 с.)

2. Абдуалиев ЭБ, Хамидов МК, ўғли Умаралиев ШМ. ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ВЛИЯНИЯ ВОДОПРОПУСКНЫХ ТРУБ НА ВЕРХНЕЕ СТРОЕНИЕ ПУТИ. InINTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. 2022 Dec 1 (Vol. 1, No. 7, pp. 141-144).

3. Мирханова ММ, Ўролов АШ. ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТЕМИР ЙЎЛЛАРИ” АЖ НИНГ ТЕЗЮРАР ВА ЮҚОРИ ТЕЗЛИКДАГИ ТЕМИР ЙЎЛЛАРИДА ХАРАКАТ ТАРКИБИДАН ТУШАЁТГАН КУЧЛАРНИ СУВ ЎТКАЗУВЧИ ҚУВУРЛАРГА ТАЪСИРИНИ ЎРГАНИШ. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. 2022 Jan 24;2(1):360-3.

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peecrp:1070589>

4. Abdualiev E, Makhamadjanov S, Uralov A. ANALYSIS OF THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF WATER PIPES IN THE RAILWAY NETWORK OF JSC" UZBEK RAILWAYS". *Involta Scientific Journal*. 2022 Feb 27;1(3):104-8.

5. Abdualiev EB, Sh UA. Culverts on the railway track <https://www.scientificprogress.uz>. In *International Scientific-Practical Distance Conference «The 21st Century Skills for Professional Activity 2021* (pp. 186-188).

6. Abdualiyev EB, Mirxanova MM. STUDIES OF THE INFLUENCE OF CULVERTS ON THE UPPER STRUCTURE OF THE PATH. *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*. 2022 Dec 1;1(9):479-83.

7. Shohjaxon Maxamadro‘zi o‘g‘li Umaraliyev, Ilhom o‘g‘li ME. TEMIR YO‘L TRANSPORTIDA BINO VA INSHOOTLAR QURILISHI. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" PLATFORM 2022 (pp. 234-237).

8. Begali o‘g‘li, Abdualiyev Elyor, and Mustafoyev Eldor Ilhom o‘g‘li. "TEMIR YO‘LLAR QURILISHIDA BETON VA TEMIRBETON VAZIFALARI." In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" PLATFORM, pp. 246-249. 2022.

9. Abdualiev EB, Khamidov MK, Eshonov FF. STUDIES OF THE INFLUENCE OF CULVERTS ON THE UPPER STRUCTURE OF THE TRACK ON THE SECTIONS OF HIGH-SPEED AND HIGH-SPEED TRAIN TRAFFIC OF JSC" UZBEKISTON TEMIR YO‘LLARI". *Results of National Scientific Research International Journal*. 2022 Dec 1;1(9):484-8.

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

[https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/
peestp:1070589](https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peestp:1070589)

10. Умаралиев Ш.М. Абдуалиев Э.Б. Performance of fasteners on high-speed and high speed stations of JSC "Uzbekistan railways" has a mixed nature «O‘ZBEKISTONDA ILM-FAN VA TA’LIM MASALALARI: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR» MAVZUSIDAGI 1-SON KONFERENSIYA MATERIALLARI 2020/7/15 (vol. 1 89-91 p.).

11. <https://academicsresearch.com/index.php/icpass/article/view/1325>

12. Abdualiyev E, Mirzahidova O, Uralov A. ELIMINATION OF IMPULSE IRREGULARITIES ON THE RAIL HEAD WITH THE HELP OF GRINDING. Academic research in educational sciences. 2021;2(2):1220-5.

13. <https://sciencebox.uz/index.php/jars/article/download/881/821/1505>

14. <https://nauka.tashiit.uz>conf2019>

15. Bekmuratovich EA. Analysis of The Technical Condition of Water Pipes in The Railway Network of JSC" Uzbek Railways". American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. 2022 Jan 26;3(1):384-7.

16. Махамаджанов ШШ, Ембергенов АБ. ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ РЕЖИМА РАБОТЫ ВОДОПРОПУСКНЫХ ТРУБ НА ЖЕЛЕЗНОДОРОЖНЫХ ЛИНИЯХ АО «УЗБЕКИСТАН ТЕМИР ЙУЛЛАРИ». BARQARORLIK VA YETAKSHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. 2022 Jan 24;2(1):411-5.

2023

DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION

SCIENTIFIC ONLINE JOURNAL

<https://sites.google.com/view/imxu/peestrp:1070589>

17. Begaliyevich AE, Shavkatovich MS, Shakarovich UA. Studies of Culverts on the High-speed Section of the Tashkent-Sirdarya Railway Line. International Journal of Human Computing Studies. 2021;3(2):18-22.

18. Умаралиев Ш.М. Абдуалиев Э.Б. Performance of fasteners on high-speed and high speed stations of JSC "Uzbekistan railways" has a mixed nature «O‘ZBEKISTONDA ILM-FAN VA TA’LIM MASALALARI: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR» MAVZUSIDAGI 1-SON KONFERENSIYA MATERIALLARI 2020/7/15:89-91.

